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OPPORTUNITIES AND PROBLEMS OF RURAL MARKETING IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

This paper is attempted to study the opportunities and problems of rural market. Rural Markets are defined as those segments of overall market of any economy, which are distinct from the other types of markets like stock market, commodity markets or Labor economics. The so-called urban markets are crowded and saturated and the share of agriculture in GDP (Gross Domestic Product) is going down but India still lives in her villages. Such a potential market was being ignored by corporate sector and small and medium industries. Hence it is proposed to study the potentiality and problems of rural market with a special reference to Indian Rural Market. The market scenario in the rural areas today is changing very rapidly. Rural consumers demand branded products mainly because of increase in disposable income and literacy level. Rural families do not like to cut their expenditure on weddings, pilgrimages, constructions and consumptions. Rural consumers have more aspirations, today this segment of buyers consumes large variety of products, both durable and non-durables and willing to pay right price for right products.

Keywords: Rural, Market, Products, Problems, Prospects, Opportunities

INTRODUCTION:

In recent years, rural markets have acquired significance, as the overall growth of the economy has resulted into substantial increase in the purchasing power of the rural communities. Rural Markets are defined as those segments of overall market of any economy, which are distinct from the other types of markets like stock market, commodity markets or Labor economics. Typically, a rural market will represent a community in a rural area with a population of 2500 to 30000. On account of green revolution, the rural areas are consuming a large quantity of industrial and urban manufactured products. In this context, a special marketing strategy, namely, rural marketing has emerged to satisfy the needs of rural consumers. Hence, it is proposed to undertake this study to find out various ways to tap the potential rural markets. The main aim of this study is to observe the potentiality of Indian Rural Markets and finding out various problems are being faced by rural markets.

DEFINING RURAL MARKETING

- National Commission on Agriculture defined Rural Marketing as —decisions to produce salable commodities involving all aspects of the market system or structure, both functional and institutional, based on technical and economic considerations and includes the pre and post harvest operationsl.

- Several Rural NGOs defined rural marketing as Marketing products produced in rural area to ur

ban areas. Or Marketing Products produced in rural areas in rural markets.

What Constitutes Rural Market?

The Census of India defines rural as habitation where population density is less than 400 per sq. Km, and where at least 75% of the male working population engaged in agriculture, and where there is not any municipality or board. Planning Commission of India defines rural as a town having population up to 15,000.

The difference between rural and urban consumers always exists in India. Most of Indian rural consumers are illiterate and poor. Illiteracy leads to inability to identify

Demographic Details of Indian Rural Markets

- 1) About 285 million live in urban India whereas 742 million reside in rural areas, constituting 72% of India's population resides in its 6, 27,000 villages.
- 2) The number of middle income and high income households in rural Indian is expected to grow from 46 million to 59 million.
- 3) Size of rural market is estimated to be 42 million households and rural market has been growing at five times the pace of the urban market.
- 4) More government rural development initiatives.
- 5) Low literacy rate
- 6) Increasing agricultural productivity leading to growth of rural disposable income.
- 7) Lowering of difference between taste of urban and rural customers.

Characteristics of Rural Marketing

Some of the important characteristics of Rural Marketing in India Economy are being listed below:

- 1) With the initiation of various rural development programmes there have been an upsurge of employment opportunities for the rural poor. One of the biggest cause behind the steady growth of rural market is that it is not exploited and also yet to be explored.
- 2) The rural market in India is vast and scattered and offers a plethora of opportunities in comparison to the urban sector. It covers the maximum population and regions and thereby, the maximum number of consumers.
- 3) The social status of the rural regions is precarious as the income level and literacy is extremely low along with the range of traditional values and superstitious beliefs that have always been a major impediment in the progression of this sector.
- 4) The steps taken by the Government of India to initiate proper irrigation, infrastructural developments, prevention of flood, grants for fertilizers, and various schemes to cut down the poverty line have improved the condition of the rural masses.

Significance of Rural Marketing:

Rural market is gaining importance as urban market is getting saturated. As due to the competition in the urban market, the market is more or so saturated as most of the capacity of the purchasers has been targeted by the marketers. So the marketers are looking for extending their product categories to an unexplored market i.e. the rural market. This has also led to the CSR activities being done by the corporate to help the poor people attain

some wealth to spend on their product categories. Here we can think of HLL (now, HUL) initiatives in the rural India. In recent years, rural markets have acquired significance in countries like China and India, as the overall growth of the economy has resulted into substantial increase in the purchasing power of the rural communities. On account of the Green Revolution in India, the rural areas are consuming a large quantity of industrial and urban manufactured products. In this context, a special marketing strategy, namely, rural marketing has taken shape. Brands rarely fight for market share in rural areas; they just have to be visible in the right place. Even expensive brands, such as Close-Up, Marie biscuits and Clinic shampoo are doing well because of deep distribution, many brands are doing well without much advertising support —. Two-thirds of Indian consumers live in rural areas and almost half of the national income is generated here. The reasons for heading into the rural areas are fairly clear. The urban consumer durable market for products like colour TVs, washing machines, refrigerators and air conditioners is growing annually at between 7 per cent and 10 per cent. The rural market is zooming ahead at around 25 per cent annually. "The rural market is growing faster than urban India now," says Venugopal Dhoot, chairman of the Rs 989 -crore (Rs billion) Videocon Appliances.

Understanding the Potential of Rural Market:

There is great potential in rural market because of the following factors:

1. Large Population : 742 million Indians constituting 138 million households reside in 6,38,365 villages (Census, 2001). The size of rural market itself speaks of its potential

2. Growth in Market: The market has been growing at 3-4% per annum adding more than one million new consumers every year. Consumer is brand loyal and understands symbols better. View it as you may, few people dispute that the rural market is massive. According to Singh, 12.2% of the world's consumers live in India. "Rural households form 72% of the total households. This puts the rural market at roughly 720 million customers." Gupta of TSMG extrapolates the Census 2001 numbers and comes up with an estimate of 790 million.

3. Impact of Globalisation: The impact of globalization will be felt in rural India as much as in urban. But it will be slow. It will have its impact on target groups like farmers, youth and women. Farmers, today 'keep in touch' with the latest information and maximize both ends..

4. Increasing Income and Purchasing Power: The agricultural development programs of the government have helped to increase income in the agricultural sector. These in turn have created greater purchasing power in rural markets.

5. Accessibility OF Market : The attraction of a market depends not only on its potential but also on its accessibility. The road network has facilitated a systemized product distribution system to villages. An increasing number of companies are supplying village markets directly. Increasing direct contacts to villages helps product promotion and availability of the product in the village shop.

6. Consumer Behavior Changes : Increased literacy and greater awareness in rural markets create new demands and discriminating buyers. This is observed more in the younger generation. In villages today, this segment of buyers consumes a large variety of products, both durables and non-durables. There is a visible increase in the consumption and use of a variety of products, which is easily observed.

7. Competition in urban markets: Intensified competition in urban markets increases costs and reduces market share.

8. New Employment Opportunities: Government schemes like IRDP (Integrated Rural Development Programme), JRY (Jawahar Rozgar Yojana) and TRYSEM (Training Rural Youth for Self Employment) have created new employment opportunities in Rural India. Co-operative banks and Public sector banks are extending

loans to rural people, thereby creating job opportunities for them. As a result very few rural people are now flocking to urban centres.

Reasons for Improvement of Business in Rural Area

- 1) Socio-economic changes (lifestyle, habits and tastes, economic status)
- 2) Literacy level (25% before independence – more than 65% in 2001)
- 3) Infrastructure facilities (roads, electricity, media)
- 4) Increase in income
- 5) Increase in expectations

Problems of Rural Markets

The development of appropriate communication systems to rural market may cost up to six times as much as reaching an urban market through established media, need rural communication facilities.

- 1) The problems of physical distribution and channel management adversely affect the service as well as the cost aspect. The existent market structure consists of primary rural market and retail sales outlet. The structure involves stock points in feeder towns to service these retail outlets at the village levels. But it becomes difficult maintaining the required service level in the delivery of the product at retail level.
- 2) Rural consumers are cautious in buying and decisions are slow and delayed. They like to give a trial and only after being personally satisfied, do they buy the product.
- 3) Culture is a system of shared values, beliefs and perceptions that influence the behavior of consumers. There are different groups based on religion, caste, occupation, income, age, education and politics and each group exerts influence on the behavior of people in villages.
- 4) As a general rule, rural marketing involves more intensive personal selling efforts compared to urban marketing. Marketers need to understand the psyche of the rural consumers and then act accordingly. To effectively tap the rural market a brand must associate it with the same things the rural folks do. This can be done by utilizing the various rural folk media to reach them in their own language and in large numbers so that the brand can be associated with the myriad rituals, celebrations, festivals, melas and other activities where they assemble.
- 5) Life in rural areas is still governed by customs and traditions and people do not easily adapt new practices. For example, even rich and educated class of farmers does not wear jeans or branded shoes.
- 6) An effective distribution system requires village-level shopkeeper, Mandal/ Taluka- level wholesaler or preferred dealer, distributor or stockiest at district level and company-owned depot or consignment distribution at state level. The presence of too many tiers in the distribution system increases the cost of distribution.
- 7) Television has made a great impact and large audience has been exposed to this medium. Radio reaches large population in rural areas at a relatively low cost. However, reach of formal media is low in rural households; therefore, the market has to undertake specific sales promotion activities in rural areas like participating in melas or fairs.
- 8) Many rural areas are not connected by rail transport. Kacha (wet) roads become unserviceable during the monsoon and interior villages get isolated.

9) There are not enough opportunities for education in rural areas. The literacy level is as low (36%) when compared to all- India average of 52%.

10) Demand for goods in rural markets depends upon agricultural situation, as agriculture is the main source of income. Agriculture to a large extent depends upon monsoon and, therefore, the demand or buying capacity is not stable or regular.

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